

COMPETENCE APPROACH IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7084324>

To think is to exercise intellectually, to work with the mind, it means to exercise mentally, taking responsibility for your own learning. It is emphasized that it is necessary to focus on mastering knowledge, but also on the development of personality, knowledge and creative abilities. It is necessary to form the basic competencies that determine its quality. The current state of the theory of foreign language teaching once again requires communicative learning in the further formation of knowledge. On the eve of the new century, the socio-cultural environment of foreign language learning in Uzbekistan has changed significantly. "the desire of the student to learn the language of another nation, the establishment of good relations between nations, who lives where is to realize that he is a representative of the people on earth, regardless of what language he speaks. Teaching a foreign language is activity-based, so communication is carried out through speech activity and serves to solve problems in the context of social interaction of communication with people. Their educational and self-educational function in general secondary education and universities, as well as their professional importance in the labor market as a whole, has increased significantly, which has led to an increase in motivation in learning international communication languages. It is the teacher who supports the student's desire to learn the language culture and communicate in French. One of the most important means of forming communicative competence in English language classes is the use of a didactic set by the teacher in the educational process. . The difficulty of learning a foreign language is that it is necessary to create conditions for the formation of communicative competence, that is, internal readiness and the ability to communicate in speech. Anyone who decides to learn a language seriously knows how to use it. Teachers also approach this process and work together with language learners, or at least those who work in this direction take a responsible approach and believe. But the belief in what you want does not mean that our belief and will are enough to achieve our goal. There is a big difference between our goal and the means we use to achieve it. To teach a language, apart from the knowledge of the target

audience, we need the conditions and environment to teach that language. A good teacher teaches, a good teacher helps to learn, and a great teacher leads by example. Fundamental socio-economic changes affecting all spheres of social life are taking place in modern Uzbekistan. The change of the state system and the formation of market economy relations determine the changes in the field of training and education of the young generation. In the theory and practice of foreign language teaching, the modernization of the educational process is being carried out on the basis of the principles that meet the new requirements of the development of society. The ability to find and expand professional information, to maintain professional competence and competence in foreign language speech activities at an appropriate level, and to constantly improve the educational process is necessary for a foreign language teacher. A foreign language teacher is always outside the natural environment of a foreign language. He is deprived of the possibility of regular qualification abroad. In fact, the analysis of demand and supply in the field of language teaching reveals its objective evolution and change. The last major turning point identified in the work known as "4,500-year history of foreign and second language teaching" was the emergence of the communicative approach. The communicative approach, which aims to "learn to communicate" in a foreign language, is still the most widely used approach to teaching French as a foreign language today. One of the strengths of this approach translates as "student-centered learning." In other words, language teaching and learning is seen as a process in which learners' language needs are prioritized, and learners use their own learning strategies according to their abilities to construct their knowledge. First of all, it is important to pay special attention to the meaning of the word "didactics". What is "didactics" itself? Didactics is the systematic study of teaching methods and practices in general, or the teaching of a particular subject or subject. Language didactics is a set of methods, approaches, hypotheses and pedagogical principles. It helps teachers, language specialists, textbook authors to optimize the processes of teaching and learning foreign languages (provide the best conditions for work). "The purpose of language didactics is to teach the conditions and methods of teaching and mastering languages in an unusual environment. In addition, it is to form students' linguistic and cultural skills." [2] € "The term "language didactics" appeared at the end of 1975. One of the main tasks specified in the program of the educational system is the acquisition of communicative competence, since the study of foreign languages in primary education is in that school. is learning to communicate in French. This

implies a communication-based approach and the gradual development of communicative competence and its components. First, we will try to define the term "competence" through the analysis of several linguists, and then French linguist Sophie Moirand we will dwell on the definition of "competency" given by is the linguistic component of textual models, i.e. knowledge and mastery (ability to use them)"[3 ,20]. For the past several years, the concept of communicative competence has been the main topic of the center of foreign language learning. The main goal is to make the language learner communicate in a foreign language. This goal is often formulated in terms of acquiring communication skills. This concept has attracted the attention of many researchers, such as many famous linguists Daniel Coste (1980), Michael Canale and Merrill Swain (1980), Sophie Moirand (1982) and others. However, until now, the concept of communicative competence has not appeared in the field of foreign language didactics. This concept originated from the ethnography of communication, a science created by the American sociolinguists Del Hymes and John Gumperz in the 60s. tried to revise, even apply. However, the remarkable success of this concept and its influence on didactics met with "much resistance and distortions"[4,9] The concept of communication competence has been greatly distorted over time. Currently, the concept of communication is discussed without using the plural concept to determine the existence of different names for this concept. From this point of view, it seemed very important to compile a brief analysis of the concept of communication competence and evaluate its practical application in the field of foreign language didactics according to its results. "Language is a tool, a useful weapon" without which there would be no real communication between people. Language is not limited to the tones of the exchanged sentences, it develops through situations and separates from the action of these situations" Anything from the outer or inner world can be expressed in language as soon as they are perceived. Situation and language are closely related. and integrated"Thus, learning to speak in a necessary situation is one of the updated methodological foundations of language teaching and learning, attracted by audio-visual approaches in the 1962s. However, the theories governing language teaching and learning at that time (structural and distributive linguistics, then generative (restorative) and transformational) do not take into account the functional dimension of linguistic expressions. Starting with the research of Del Jaimes, "the concept of communicative competence was rapidly applied and redefined in foreign language didactics"[3]. The concept of communicative competence has become the most important concept for

teaching and learning French as a foreign language. The main goal of teaching is to encourage the student to communicate in a foreign language. However, as we noted above, this concept of ethnography of communication in foreign language didactics has not been defined and therefore does not know a single general definition and presentation. During primary education, students need to develop communicative and linguistic skills that enable them to function and succeed in their environment personally and socially, and to form the foundations and foundations of citizenship. In this way, competence-based approaches and learning system projects help to develop the communicative and intercultural competence of each student, give them the opportunity to acquire new knowledge, the basic, integral and other languages of development in the implementation of the model of multilingualism and intercultural education. is a means of effective communication in a variety of environments with appropriate speakers.

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